

VALORIFICATION OF THE KINDERGARTEN- SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL PARTNERSHIP IN PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SCHOOLING

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Abstract

The article addresses the issue regarding the valorification of the partnership between the pre-school and primary education institution in order to ensure the quality of the children's preparation for school. The paper analyzes concepts such as: educational partnership, preparation for school, school maturity; there are highlighted the defining notes of the kindergarten-school educational partnership, the specificity of the kindergarten-school continuity; it is presented a kindergarten-school educational partnership project focused on the optimization of the process of preparing children for schooling.

Keywords: educational partnership, kindergarten-school partnership, kindergarten-school continuity, preparation of children for school, school maturity, educational aptitude, educational partnership project.

1. Introduction

Considered increasingly not only as a distinctive and necessary stage of the education system, but also as an integral part of global educational structures, as a first phase of the permanent education, the preschool education reevaluates its objectives, content, teaching technology in the perspective of new educational policies. Taking into account both the permanent educational incidents with the preschool education, as well as the repercussions of the preschool education on the permanent education, it appears the necessity of establishing a stage of child's preparation for the primary school and the problem of the preschoolers' qualitative preparation for schooling is becoming more and more pressing.

Preparing the child for school is an actual issue of concern to psychologists, pedagogues, psycho-pedagogues, parents whose purpose is to prepare the preschoolers for schooling, so that this preparation will ensure their successful adaptation to the new school environment.

The problem of preparation for school places the child in the foreground, as a subject of learning, on whom several factors and educational agents influence, either directly or indirectly, but which serve the same purpose, namely ensuring continuity of interventions, in which to take into account the children's psycho-socio-physical peculiarities and which will ensure not only the child's special preparation for schooling, but also the general preparation for the future schooler status.

The kindergarten, as a transition stage between the family and the school, trains the child in tasks similar to the school ones, but given in the form of play, it increases his intellectual availability, activates him mentally and motivationally, puts him in contact with the preparatory requests for school, contributing to the premises creation of the beginning of schooling in the conditions of an optimal preparation of the child (Golu, 2009, p. 188).

We share the opinion of the researcher Golu (2009, p. 183) who argues that the degree of difficulty felt by the 6-7 year old child at the beginning of school is proportional with the experience he acquired until entering school. In such circumstances, the significance of the process of preparing the child for school is amplified, which requires the subject to a staggered distribution of forces and energy consumption and a progressive exercise of adaptive mechanisms, contexts that can be ensured by the valorification of the kindergarten-school educational partnership.

2. Preparation for school: conceptual boundaries

Doron and Parot (2007, pp. 600-601) emphasize the need for a psychological preparation which represents "the set of processes whose objective is to establish a psychological state favorable to achieving maximum performance on the occasion of a competition".

The child's psychological preparation for the school activity begins, in fact, within the family, where the first tasks of intellectual, moral, aesthetic, physical education are performed. The material, social, cultural conditions, affective atmosphere in the family have a great influence on the child's psychic development. First the family, then, in an organized way, the kindergarten contributes to the enrichment of the volume of knowledge and representations, by exercising and stimulating the cognitive, motivational processes and familiarizing the child with the simplest techniques of intellectual activity. Next, the school makes the most of the acquisitions of the previous stage by replacing the game with learning, as a dominant activity and by efforts to mitigate the important differences regarding the requirements, the offer and the educational program, the evaluation and interrelation mode (Goran, 2010, para 4.) .

Constantinescu (1981), is of the opinion that the preparation for school means ensuring those internal conditions that give the subject the optimal opportunity to successfully tackle future tasks or types of requests or difficulties. This general availability can also be manifested as a positive psychological orientation or montage in relation to a future situation, to which the subject adheres with "the whole of his intellectual, affective, volitional, psychomotor forces " (Chez Comşa & Mihai, 2006, p. 10).

Păun (1990) argues that " the preparation for school means, firstly, a state of readiness for the learning activity, the provision of internal conditions that give the child the opportunity to optimally address the demands of the new activity, but also that positive psychological state necessary for school beginning. Also, ensuring those conditions that allow the child to adapt to the specific of the class as a social group ”.

Gutkina (2004) highlights the need to ensure the psychological preparation for school, which occurs at the border between preschool and small school age and, which, first of all, manifests itself in the presence of the child's motivation, especially for the learning activity, allowing him or her to be effectively involved in the educational process and indicating that the development of the intellectual sphere of the child's personality is sufficient to start school.

Moşanu & Liogchii (2013, p. 190) argue that at the moment of entering the school the child must possess a set of prior behaviors, including physical development according to the age level and a good state of health. In this context, the researchers evaluated the level of physical condition and the potential of the cardiovascular system adaptation of the children of the age of 6-7 years.

The child's preparation in the kindergarten should be understood as a process of developing those skills and abilities, which will allow an easy

adaptation of the children to the requirements of the first class. Such preparation is based on the requirements regarding the continuity between the first two stages of our education system. For this, it is necessary the adequate correlation of the psycho-pedagogical factors of the continuity: the knowledge of the age peculiarities; the observation of the principle of stage development of the personality; the assurance of the children's preparation for school; gradual dosing of influences in the educational process; the unity of educational aims and contents operationalized in pre-school education and incipient primary education; the discovery of new relationships between the educator and teacher; the use of the child's skills at the beginning of school, and their evolutionary development strengthens the continuity relation between the preschool and school institution (Manolescu et al., 2013, pp. 10-11).

Golu, Zlate and Verza (1995, pp. 110-111) state that at the beginning of the primary education, it is possible to reach the discrepancy levels of children's preparation for the adaptation to the school tasks, which can be expressed either in the fact that the establishment of the premises of the transition to education occurs before the formal connection to the new activity and then, the child, dissatisfied with the reality of his old social position (preschool), pays less attention to the game, replacing it with other activities until he comes into contact with the school, or the formation of the premises remains behind the formal transition to non-school activities and then, the child, going to school in conditions of insufficient psychological maturation (training), feels dissatisfaction from his new social position (of school), which he perceives as a frustrating factor, that of interrupting the continuity of the pleasant activity, the game.

The discrepancy between the social-objective pole (the position of status and role) and the psychological-subjective pole (the level of internal education

for school) generates dissonances for both categories of children, who are on the threshold of schooling. They will go through a critical phase, of crisis, with different motivational meanings for them: the first experiencing dissatisfaction, emotional discomfort as a result of the prolongation of an occupational status-role that started to be no longer accepted, the second category living the discomfort due to the failures and embarrassing situations that create an occupational status-role that didn't start to be not accepted. Consequently, negative behavioral symptoms will appear in both cases.

We consider that the children's qualitative preparation for school by approaching this complex process from a two-dimensional perspective (general preparation for school / special preparation for school) ensures the school maturity of the children at the beginning of the primary education, creating an easy context for the children's school adaptation.

The *general preparation* for school training involves: physical and physiological preparation, intellectual, social, affective, motivational, moral-volitional preparation, etc.

The *special preparation* for the subsequent school activity involves the knowledge assimilation by the child, the formation of the capacities and the attitudes, that is to say the competences, which will ensure the success of the learning of the basic disciplines in the first class. In this context, the formation of the reading and writing premises and the formation of elementary mathematical representations have priority.

Maturation is seen as a system of bio-psycho-social processes, leading to individual evolution, and during this process, a crucial role is played by the genetic programming (which, under conditions of balance with the environment, promotes functional growth and organization), as well as by the environmental conditions, learning and education activity, decisive for humans. Maturation is

the result of two concomitant processes, one at the anatomical (biological) level and the other at the neuro-psycho-physiological level, which consists in organizing the great neuropsychological systems due to a learning mechanism, under the influence of stimuli and education. We must also add the specific, psychosocial meaning of maturation, materialized in the regulation of conduct in accordance with the norms and requirements imposed by the collectivity, by the existential social environment (Golu, 2009, p. 47).

Cristea (2000) argues that school maturity is one of the favoring factors of school adaptation and implies the full exploitation of the level of biological, psychological, social and cultural development specific to the respective age and stage of education.

Ștefan (2006, p. 210) is of the opinion that school maturation "is expressed by more cognitive, affective-motivational and attitudinal competences, necessary for the child when entering the first class".

Bolboceanu and Vrânceanu (1996) state that school maturity expresses the degree of agreement between the level of development of the child and the school requirements specific to the first class.

Researchers Vengher L., Vengher A. and Kolominskii (1994) highlight in the structure of psychological maturity the following components:

1. *The maturity of the personality*, which includes the formation of children's readiness to receive the new social position - the position of pupil, who has his rights and obligations. This maturity is manifested in the attitude of the child towards the school, towards the learning activity, towards the teacher, towards himself; it also includes a certain level of motivational sphere development (motivation for learning must be developed); it involves a certain level of emotional sphere development (emotional stability).

2. *Intellectual maturity*, which concerns differentiated perception; analytical thinking; logical memory; the interest towards knowledge, towards the process of its acquisition; possession of oral language; development of gentle hand movements and visual-motor coordination.

3. The social-psychological maturity, which includes the formation of those qualities in the child, which help him to communicate with his peers, with the adults; it involves the possession of the ability to interact with others; the ability to give in and defend himself, the ability to obey the interests and habits of the group (beside Vîrlan, 2005, p. 67).

According to the scheme of school maturity after Bernart (apud Bolboceanu & Vrînceanu, 1996, p.67), the mature personality for school must be characterized by the following moments: *physical maturity* - resistance to effort; *mental maturity* - the capacity for analysis and planning, understanding the norm, the rule, the quantities; *volitional maturity* - the ability to self-regulate, inhibit his impulses and regulate his needs; *social maturity* - the need to belong to the group, appropriate social conduct in the group; *moral maturity* - the feeling of duty and responsibility, awareness of pregnancy; *maturity for work* - perseverance, attention, need for performance.

In the acceptance of the researcher Cemortan (2008, pp. 40-41), an important aspect of the educational actions carried out in the preschool institutions in order to ensure the children's school maturity is the formation of the basic behaviors for this age:

- *Social behavior*: the formation of moral qualities and character traits; revealing and respecting the position of another human being; cultivating the conscious discipline, the ability to understand the rights and obligations; preparing the child for the new social status, the school one, and respecting this role in the training process; the formation of the ability to appreciate from the moral and civic point

of view his own behaviour and that of the colleagues; the faculty to respect the interests and the rules established by the children group

- *Affective behavior*: the degree of emotional sphere development (the ability to control his emotions); the level of motivational preparation; the child's positive attitude towards school, the desire to acquire new knowledge; the subordination of motives, in the hierarchical system whose motives and cognitive interests begin to become dominant; the formation of the mechanisms of the regulation of the volitional actions (minimizing impulsive reactions, the ability to subordinate and prioritize actions, the possibility of overcoming difficulties, the degree of independence, the ability to act appropriately when assessing the task performed, the ability to analyze independently the result obtained, the observance of certain norms of conduct);

- *Cognitive behavior*: the presence of representations and knowledge about the environment (important is not the volume, but the quality, the degree of generalization of knowledge, the child's ability to manipulate with it internally); the possession of the initial elements of analytical thinking, the ability to highlight the general characteristics of objects and the relationships between phenomena; the orientation by model in the working process, the ability to copy the exact model and to work according to the rule; the level of preparation for conscious regulation of cognitive activity; the presence of cognitive interests and the premises of creativity; the possession of sensory and intellectual means; the sensory experience; the possession of perception actions oriented to the analysis of objects, phenomena, properties and relations between objects and phenomena; the successful use of the system of sensory standards; the formation of visual-motor coordination, the perception of the object in the space; the ability to focus attention on the activity.

- *Verbal behavior*: the development of the language semantic and communicative function; the practical possession of all aspects of the mother tongue (vocabulary, phonetic culture, grammatical correctness, coherent expressive language); the presence and degree of language forms development; literary development (perception, elementary analysis, reproduction of texts); the formation of literary language; the association of speech sounds with their corresponding signs (letters); the formation of reading and writing premises; the development of verbal creativity.
- *Motor behavior*: the orientation in time and space; the possession of basic motor skills and qualities; the formation of the habit of independent exercise; the auditory-motor coordination; the harmonious physical development, the formation and improvement of psychomotor capacities; health fortification, the formation of health and hygiene skills.

Cermoran (2013, pp. 8-9) notes that in the children's preparation for school, the formation of learning competences is relevant, in the context of which the subject's knowledge, abilities and attitudes play an important role. Thus, at the end of preschooling, in addition to a volume of knowledge and skills, the child must possess an elementary level of attitudes. Also, it is necessary not only an intellectual and affective preparation of the child, but also a volitional preparation, which is supported by an adequate, appropriate belief that forms a positive attitude towards learning, educates his curiosity and the desire to learn, love of books, it forms his activism. Only in such cases we can positively appreciate the child's degree of preparation for school, we can argue that the preschooler was trained with the most elementary learning skills, the basis of school maturity.

Botnari (2013, p. 6-7) argues that "the methodology of forming the learning competence must focus on enhancing the resources of the subject,

consisting of knowledge ("to know"), skills, abilities ("to do") and attitudes, values ("to be", "to become") in a concrete situation in which the subject realizes this potential". In the efficient formation of the learning competence, the educators/teachers are urged to respect the following "constructivist principles: the principle of mental construction priority; the principle of autonomy and individualization/personalization; the principle of contextual learning; the principle of collaborative learning; the principle of priority of formative, dynamic evaluation".

The aptitude for schooling or school maturity requires the acquisition of the skills, skills and abilities necessary for the school activity based on learning (Mogonea, 2016, p. 9)

The schooling aptitude is a concept with a dynamic content, always at the intersection between the level of the child's development at the age of school debut and the volume, the level of the demands of the first class; it expresses a certain level of the general development of the child of 6-7 years which, through the specific requests of the school-type activity, makes possible the further harmonious development of all the dimensions of his personality (Comşa & Mihai, 2006, p. 11).

The aptitude of schooling aims on the one hand the adaptation as a result of a succession of transformations of the child under a bio-psycho-social relationship, and on the other hand, it concerns the fund, the volume of knowledge that the child has about the environment and which will constitute a starting point and the premises for further learning and development. Thus, the aptitude for schooling is the result of the interaction between learning and development, between the instructional-educational approach and its consequences in the psychic development plan (Goran, 2010, para 4.).

Coaşan & Vasilescu (1988, p. 30) state: " The adaptation to the first class involves not only the proper development of cognitive psychic processes, of the most important operations and qualities of thinking, of intellectual qualities, of the formation of intellectual work skills (to observe, to listen to the demands of the adult, to act correctly on their basis, to answer questions, to formulate them, to appreciate, to complete the colleagues' answers), but also the intervention of the affective-motivational and volitional peculiarities."

Radu (1976, p. 53) states that the schooling aptitude, being not limited only to the child's intellectual-cognitive preparation in order to assimilate the content of the training, is, a much more complex notion that relates to the multidimensional state of the child's personality including the affective, volitional and social sphere. In this context, the degree of the development of the interests of knowing the child as a support of a sustained learning motivation, the orientation in the environment, the child's sociability, which make him able to adjust his activity according to the requirements of the adult, of the school program as well as to carry out a group activity, a certain degree of motor development and others, complete the general picture of the schooling aptitude.

Mihai (2010, p. 31) considers that "a child apt for schooling: perceives; understands; thinks; evaluates; makes decisions; acts; adequately verbalizes what he wants to communicate; he expresses correctly: thoughts, desires, intentions, emotional experience; he has a mastery of language as a tool for: information, communication, expression; he classifies and sorts objects according to different criteria; he uses the concepts of time and space correctly; he operates frequently with terms that express quantity ratios: much, little, higher, smaller."

Burlea and Milici (2008, p. 5) are of the opinion that "the approach of the concept of the schooling aptitude as a foundation on general education (the formation of learning competences, the sensory and cognitive education, the

communication and language development, the psychomotor education) and the special training (the formation of the reading-writing premises, the formation of mathematical representations) increase the value of the process of preparing the children for learning in school. In order to ensure continuity in the formation and development of schooling skills for children aged 5-7 years, it is necessary to gradually measure the influence on children in the learning process and to develop a system of relations between the educator and teacher with a view of aiming at adopting educational strategies meant to facilitate the learning process at the next stage."

The preparation for school is therefore a complex problem that aims at ensuring the formation of an extensive range of availability that ensures the child the success of the school start.

We believe that the efficiency of the process of preparing children for school, with maximum impact on ensuring their later adaptation to the school start, will increase if the following psycho-pedagogical conditions are met:

- Emphasis will be placed on both the special preparation and the children's general preparation for school.

- The continuity between the activity of the preschool institution and the primary school will be ensured, by the valorification of the kindergarten-school partnership project focused on the effective preparation of preschoolers for schooling, with an impact on enhancing the quality of the child's subsequent adaptability to the school status. Within the respective project, the teaching staff from the two educational institutions will be included in various common activities such as: methodical meetings, seminars, roundtables, consultations, workshops, trainings, conferences, mutual attendance of educators and teachers to didactic and extradidactic activities with the acquisition of the advanced experience and of the good practices in the children's preparation for school with

a view of a quality school adaptation afterwards. Also, the involvement of preschoolers and small schoolchildren in various joint activities will be monitored.

3. The educational partnership: terminological benchmarks

The partnership represents "the cooperation in an action of common interest" (Ştefan, 2006, p. 246).

Kaşlenko (2004) argues that the partnership represents constructive cooperation, characterized by common interests, goals and values, based on the benevolent character and the persistence in time of the relationships assuming the responsibilities of all parties towards the achieved result.

The partnership constitutes: "a commitment in a negotiated joint action; a contribution of resources, of exchanges, of contacts, of associated networks in constructive terms; a negotiation between the parties having the power to contract with a recognized interlocutor; an agreement of mutual collaboration between equal partners working together to achieve their own interests, solving common problems; an institutional framework for solving common problems, through a coherent action, starting from the definition of the framework objectives within a certain time, with the clear distribution of responsibilities and evaluation procedures" (Cristea, 2000, p. 280).

Vrasmaş (2008, p. 19) is of the opinion that the educational partnership aims at "the form of communication, cooperation and collaboration in the child's support at the level of the educational process, which involves a unit of educational requirements, options, decisions and actions between educational factors".

Cuzneţov (2002, p. 13) states that the partnership represents "a social relationship that includes a set of interrelations of educational agents, thus ensuring the social integration of the subject".

The educational partners also contribute to the stimulation and consolidation of all aspects involved in the three dimensions: intellectual, affective and relational. The action of the educational partners is always required to be coordinated so that they may have the opportunity to manifest themselves in solidarity and complementarity, each acting through the specific means available to them (Nicola, 2000, p.108).

Cojocaru (2003, p. 976) argues that a clear distinction must be made between *partnership and collaboration*. The partnership has several characteristics: it is a *relationship established* between two or more persons, institutions, groups that put together certain resources to achieve a common goal. It is always born of the desire to solve a certain social problem by outlining the tasks, obligations and rights of each partner. It involves the input of the factors involved, depending on the real possibilities of each individual; it is an *equality relationship* because no subordination relations are established; *both partners evaluate* the degree of achievement of the common objectives and the *management of the resources*; it is concluded for *a relatively long period* of time; there is *permanent communication*; the responsibilities are assumed by the partners to fulfill the objectives of the joint program; each partner assumes *the risks and failures of the program*; there is a policy established for *the common promotion of the common image* of the program; it is a relationship that imposes *a high degree of rigidity* in changing the objectives and activities established within the program; it presents a *high stability, a low risk of dissolution* of the partnership until the end of the program; it presents *the security of a common medium or long term strategy* when the program has achieved its objectives.

The collaboration is distinguished from the partnership by several significant differences: it is a relationship established between two or more persons, institutions, groups that have *different purposes*, but in order to achieve them, they need the support of others; it is an *unequal relationship* between those who cooperate because the resources are not common and each manages their resources to achieve their own purpose; within the collaboration, *each participant evaluates their own objectives and manages their own resources*; it has a *punctual character*, it does not have a permanent character; in a collaborative relationship, *the communication is fragmented*; each collaborator assumes the responsibilities from the perspective of his/her current program; each collaborator assumes *the risks and failures* for his own activities, and not for those of the program; each practices an *individualized promotion* of their own programs; i) the collaboration implies a greater flexibility offered by the existence of different objectives for each participant; it aims at an *unstable relationship* and there is a risk of dissolution of the relationship when a participant does not reach his / her own goals; it is characterized by short-term strategies.

4. The kindergarten-school educational partnership focused on the optimization of the process of preparing children for schooling: defining notes

The core value of the partnership between the preschool and primary education institution is the continuity of the kindergarten-school.

According to Cristea (2015, p. 599), "the continuity between the school levels and stages represents the general objective strategically committed to the construction of modern education systems, promoted especially in the case of designing and carrying out school reforms, in any historical context determined from the psychological and social point of view. Its non-realization, materialized

in the discontinuities that appear between different levels and school stages, constitutes a cause and an expression of the crisis in which there was a system of education, in a certain stage of evolution / involution that imposes its reform as its solution".

The continuity assurance involves "facilitating the pupils' adaptation to the conditions of organization, planning, realization and development of their own education to a new level of education" (Cristea, 2015, p. 601).

The continuity between the preschool and primary education is achieved through common goals, through similar contents and methods. Both the forms of organization and development of some activities, as well as the educational methods and the contents of the preschool education anticipate the primary cycle. The generalization of the inclusion of all the children of 5-6 years in the educational system facilitates the social integration of the child and ensures the continuity between the two stages of the education system. From a psychosomatic point of view, the two stages of age (preschool and small school) have many common features, which ensure the element of educational continuity: the 3-year-old child, first confronted with the difficulties of adapting to the collective life, at the time of entry at the kindergarten, will integrate more easily, faster in the school system. The beginning of the child's socialization in the kindergarten, the diversification of the human relations (child-adult relations, child-children relations) continue in the primary cycle, within the organized framework of learning. The human relations become more complex, they are structured on professional criteria. These new relationships require the development of verbal and nonverbal communication skills, as well as the formation of civilized behavioral skills, while deepening self-awareness (Manolesu et al., 2013, pp. 8-9).

In order to ensure the effective partnership between educators and teachers focused on the optimization of the process of preparing children for schooling "it is necessary to make common kindergarten-school actions, such as: presenting video cassettes with aspects from the reception of children on the first day of school, having invited the pupils of the first class and their teacher; attendance at a reading, math, writing activity; organizing evaluation activities - contests that take place with the first class (customs and Christmas carols, sports competitions, the first of June); walks around the neighborhood; country trips; dramatizations, in which the role of the pupil was interpreted by the preschool child; making cards on the occasion of 8 of March etc. " (Manolescu et al., 2013, p. 11).

The preparatory class aims, by its specificity, at adapting the child to the school demands proposed by the learning activities with a finalist, organized and systematic character. The focus of the educational process on the child in the preparatory class should be reflected in the approach of the curriculum from the perspective of global development and should aim at including all the important aspects of the complete development of the child, in accordance with his or her individual and age peculiarities. The emphasis placed on capacities and attitudes development related to socio-emotional development (living and working together or with others, managing emotions, respecting diversity), the physical development (fine and coarse motor skills, but also health and healthy food) or the development of the attitudes and abilities in learning (curiosity and interest, initiative, persistence in activity, creativity), along with traditionally pursued academic competences (in the field of cognitive and language and communication development) require the teaching staff to rethink the educational approach, the specific modalities of organizing the learning and teaching process, as well as the specific evaluation modalities at this level of schooling. The

transition from games to learning does not have to be abrupt; the passage must be achieved gradually, by introducing in the activities of the type of game some sequences of the active learning of conscious voluntary effort, which will anticipate systematic organized learning steps, integrated in improved learning strategies, accompanied by evaluative processes organically inserted in the instructive-educative activities (Manolescu et al., 2013, p. 21).

Our concern for streamlining the process of preparing children for schooling in order to subsequently adapt them to the demands of the school environment has determined us to develop and implement a kindergarten-school partnership project with the topic "Preparing children for school - a priority condition in ensuring school adaptation".

The aim of the project was to support and promote the efficient and constructive cooperation of the teaching staff from the preschool institution and the primary school in order to ensure the qualitative preparation of children for schooling.

The objectives of the project were:

- determining the interconnection of the objectives, contents, methods of teaching-learning-evaluation and the forms of the organization of the didactic activity specific to the two stages of education in order to ensure continuity in the preparation of preschool children for the new pupil status;
- common participation of the teaching staff from the kindergarten and primary school in various activities (roundtables, seminars, methodical meetings, workshops, individual and group consultations, trainings, etc.) focused on the problem of the efficient preparation of children for facilitating subsequent school adaptation;

- taking advanced experience through the mutual attendance of educators and teachers to public activities and lessons in order to ensure the continuity of the educational process in the two educational institutions;
- making direct contacts between preschool children with young pupils (especially with the first class pupils), focusing on common participation in various didactic and extradidactic activities (conducting exhibitions, competitions, festivities, making reciprocal visits, etc.).

Beneficiaries:

- direct: the teaching staff from the pre-primary and primary education;
- indirect: children of preschool age; pupils of young school age; children's parents.

Resources:

- human: the project coordinator, the managers and the methodologists of the institutions, the educators who work in the pre-school groups, the teachers of the first - fourth classes, the preschoolers in the preparatory group for school, the pupils of small school age, children's parents.
- materials: the entire material basis of the institutions involved in the project; objective didactic means: cardboard, colored pencils, pens, etc.; imaginary didactic means: sheets, worksheets for children and teachers, images with story sequences, etc.; audio-visual didactic means: computer, video projector, camera, etc.

Strengths:

- Ensuring the opportunity to increase the teaching staff professional competences in the field of the children's efficient preparation for optimizing their subsequent adaptability to the educational environment in the primary school;
- Favoring the increase of the level of preschool children's preparation for school;

Risks: lack of some teaching staff's interest and motivation to cooperate and collaborate in order to make the process of preparing the children more efficient for the adaptation to the subsequent school activity.

Expected results:

- ensuring the continuity between the activity of the pre-school institution and the primary school in the process of preparing children for school;
- increasing the level of general education for school (physical, cognitive, socio-affective, motivational, volitional, etc.) and preschoolers' special preparation for school (the formation of reading and writing premises, the development of language and oral communication; the formation of elementary mathematics representations) for optimal school adaptation;
- increasing the interest of educators and teachers in the problem of children's general and special preparation in order to ensure the subsequent school adaptation.

Among the most effective forms of kindergarten-primary school partnership implemented in order to optimize the process of preparing children for school, we can mention:

- Joint activities of the teaching staff: Roundtable "Preparing for school - an imperative of modern preschool education"; Individual and group consultations on the issue of preparing children for school; The psycho-pedagogical council with the theme "Valences of the kindergarten-school-family partnership in preparing children for schooling"; The seminar "Diagnosis of school maturity of children from preschool and primary education"; The seminar "Incursion into the problem of the school adaptation of the first class pupils"; Psycho-social training "Preparation for school versus school adaptation"; Workshop "We are together in the children's effective preparation for school".

- Joint activities of preschool and small children: the involvement of preschoolers in the organization of school holidays: "Good morning, school", "Goodbye, dear abecedar"; the involvement of the children of small school age in the celebration "Goodbye, dear kindergarten"; the joint organization of trips, walks, entertainments with a well-defined purpose; the organization of school visits in order to familiarize preschoolers with the school environment and to form correct representations about school.

For carrying out the above mentioned partnership project, we respected certain conditions exposed by different researchers (Cuznețov, 2002; Băran-Pescaru, 2004; Vrasmaș, 2008) regarding the facilitation of the interaction between the educational partners, which we considered to be valuable in the optimization of the process of preparing children for schooling in the context of the valorification of the kindergarten-school educational partnership:

Cuznețov (2002) mentions the following conditions which, being respected, contribute to the efficiency of the relationship between partners: respecting the ethical norms and the requirements of the Code of ethics of the educational partnership; ensuring the prospective and continuous character of the educational partnership; ensuring the flexibility, dynamism and empathy that would become defining characteristics of the educational partnership.

Băran-Pescaru (2004) highlights the contexts that make the cooperation between educational partners more efficient, among which we list: the efficient communication, overcoming time and resources constraints, partners differences; the meticulous planning, flexibility, continuity, persistence, consistency and diversity of joint actions undertaken in order to solve the problem of common interest; the current evaluation of the effectiveness of the educational partnership forms implemented and the continuous monitoring of the project.

Vrasmaş (2008, p.219) lists the following conditions that optimize the educational partnership: interactions accepted by all partners; the effective collaboration - a common action in which each one has a different role; the effective cooperation - a common action in which interrelationships and common roles are exercised.

The mediatization of the educational partnership project was achieved by: the popularization of the idea of necessity and the results of the kindergarten-school educational partnership within methodical meetings, scientific and practical conferences; cooperative activities between educators and teachers in various publications.

The evaluation of the kindergarten-school partnership project aimed at:

- a) Evaluating the degree of the teaching staff involvement and interest for the proposed project. Modality: observation method, investigation.
- b) Evaluating the impact of the project on the children's preparation for school. Modality: questioning, observation, testing, analysis of children's activity products.
- c) Summative evaluation. Modality: carrying out a final analysis of the project in order to reveal the relationship between the proposed objectives and the attested results

5. Conclusions

1. The preparation for school is a complex process specific to the preschool age, focused on the two-dimensional approach (general education, special education), which acquires a particular connotation in the context of the subsequent adaptation of the child to the demands of the new school status.
2. The efficiency of the process of preparing children for schooling increases significantly in the case of ensuring the continuity between the activity of the

preschool institution and the primary school, through the valorification of the effective educational partnership between educators and teachers.

3. The kindergarten-school partnership involves the determination of the interconnection of the objectives, contents, forms of instruction, methods and teaching aids in order to prepare children for schooling; it aims at establishing direct contacts between the educators from the preschool institution and the primary school based on the analysis of the Curriculum of the two institutions, on the selection, systematization and elaboration of the teaching-learning-evaluation technologies, on the exchange of experience between the educators and teachers; it provides direct contacts between the children of preschool age with the pupils of the first class through joint participation in various didactic and extradidactic activities

4. The efficient communication, constructive, coherent and persistent cooperation of the educators from the pre-school institution and teachers from the primary school, involved in various common activities (methodical meetings, psycho-pedagogical councils, seminars, workshops, consultations, roundtables, attendance to didactic and extradidactic activities etc.) lead to the efficiency of the children's preparation process for schooling, which has maximum impact on their subsequent quality school adaptation to the school start.

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